

Multimodal Engagement and sustainable Lifestyle Interventions Optimizing breast cancer Risk reduction supported by Artificial intelligence

Deliverable 8.6 – Policy Brief Formulating Recommendations v.01

Deliverable No.	D8.6	Due Date	M11 – November 2024
Description	Policy brief formulating recommendations based on the research of the innovation strand of the “Prevention & early detection (behavioural change)” annual cluster meeting year 1.		
Type	R- Document, report	Dissemination Level	PU- Public
Work Package No.	8	Work Package Title	Recommendations & Dissemination
Version	1	Status	Final
Lead Beneficiary	15. EHMA	Main Contact	Alexandra Olson

Document Information

Project Number	101136791
Acronym	MELIORA
Full name	Multimodal Engagement and sustainable Lifestyle Interventions Optimizing breast cancer Risk reduction supported by Artificial intelligence - MELIORA
Start date of the project	01.01.2024
Project duration	January 2024-December 2027
Project URL	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101136791
EU project officer	Laura GARCIA IBANEZ

Date of delivery	Contractual: M11- November 2024	Actual: M11- November 2024
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Keywords	Cluster, policy brief, MELIORA, Prevention, Early detection, cancer
Lead editor	EHMA

Statement of originality

Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the first version of policy recommendations developed from the annual meeting of the Prevention and Early Detection (Behavioral Change) cluster, held in Barcelona, Spain, on September 17, 2024. Established under the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, this cluster unites three key projects—iBeChange, MELIORA, and SUNRISE— that focus on innovative strategies for cancer prevention and early detection. As an initial iteration, this report outlines the policy recommendations proposed by each project, details the processes that informed their development, identifies shared overarching themes, and evaluates their potential impact. Recognizing the evolving nature of this work, the recommendations will be continuously refined and enhanced based on ongoing research and collaboration within the cluster. The annual cluster meeting for the Prevention and Early Detection Cluster (the cluster) was held in Barcelona on September 17th 2024, during the iBeChange annual meeting. This cluster, created under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, includes three key projects - iBeChange, MELIORA and SUNRISE - focused on the development of innovative strategies for cancer prevention and early detection. The current report is aiming to summarize the key points discussed during the first annual cluster meeting, including research updates, collaborative efforts, challenges and future directions.

Disclaimer

The present document does not in any way overrule the Grant Agreement (including the Annexes associated) and the Consortium Agreement.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial intelligence
BC	Breast Cancer/ Behavioural Change
Cluster	Prevention & early detection (behavioural change) cluster
DMP	Data management plan
EAB	External Advisory Board
EAC	Ethics Advisory Committee
EAPM	European Alliance for Personalized Medicine
EBCP	Europe's Beating Cancer Plan
EHMA	European Health Management Association
EM	Emotional management
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679
HUA	Harakopio University of Athens
i-HD	European Institute for Innovation through Health Data
IEAB	Independent Ethical Advisory Board
IEO	European Institute of Oncology
IOCN	Institutul Oncologic Prof Ion Chiricuta Cluj-Napoca
PBY	PredictBy
SPAB	European Stakeholder and Advisory Board
VCIs	Virtual Coach Interventions
WP	Work Package
SWOT Analysis	Analysis of Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats
ISGF	Swiss Research Institute for Public Health and Addiction
ECAC	European Code Against Cancer
LMIC	Low-and Middle-Income Countries
ENVI	Committee on the Environment, Public Health, and Food Safety
SANT	Subcommittee on Public Health

2. Introduction

Cancer arises from both genetic and environmental factors, significantly shaped by daily lifestyle choices. Adopting a balanced diet, engaging in regular exercise, avoiding smoking and alcohol, and practicing sun protection all contribute to reducing cancer risk. Early diagnosis is equally vital, as targeted screenings for various types of cancer can detect the disease in its early stages, where treatment success rates are notably higher. Prevention and early detection are thus essential tools in cancer control. Together, promoting healthy lifestyles and raising awareness can play a pivotal role in decreasing cancer incidence and improving survival rates, ultimately enhancing quality of life and reducing the global burden of cancer. This report, titled the Common Work Plan for Scientific Collaboration within the "Prevention & Early Detection (Behavioural Change)" Cluster, outlines the collaborative framework of three Horizon Europe projects: iBeChange, MELIORA, and SUNRISE. These projects were selected for their strategies, best practices, and insights designed to reduce disparities in cancer prevention and early detection.

This approach aligns with the EU Mission on Cancer, which aims to improve the lives of over three million people by 2030 through prevention, effective treatment, and quality-of-life improvements. The report is organized into three main parts. The first part introduces the structure and objectives of the deliverable, setting the context of the EU Cancer Mission and providing an overview of the three projects, iBeChange, MELIORA, and SUNRISE, with a description of their individual goals and areas of intervention. The second part focuses on the Prevention and Early Detection Cluster, particularly the Behavioural Change aspect, detailing the framework and tools established to foster collaboration. These tools include shared workspaces, coordinated contact points, and a schedule of milestones, all aimed at improving cooperation and consolidating best practices across projects. Partner competencies are mapped to enhance synergy and ensure a cohesive approach to cancer prevention. The third part describes each of the Cluster's work strands—Research and Innovation, Citizen Engagement, Addressing Inequalities, Communication and Dissemination, and Data Management—detailing objectives, roles, activities, deliverables, and timelines for each. This comprehensive work plan guides collaborative efforts across projects, helping overcome barriers to sustainable behavioural change in cancer prevention and early detection. The Cancer Mission of Horizon Europe integrates advanced strategies in research, public health, data sharing, and citizen engagement.

As part of Europe's Beating Cancer Plan, it aims to enable over three million people to live longer and healthier lives by 2030 through targeted prevention, effective treatments, and

quality-of-life support for families affected by cancer. This mission focuses on clear, achievable objectives and realistic goals. The Cluster's contribution to the "Prevention" objective of the EU Cancer Mission canters on promoting sustainable behavioural changes to reduce cancer risk. Behavioural change efforts encompass healthy diet adoption, increased physical activity, and reduced smoking, addressing complex challenges at both the individual and systemic levels. These challenges include motivation, cultural and economic factors, healthcare access, policy conditions, and community support, each affecting the potential to adopt and maintain healthier behaviors.

The projects iBeChange, MELIORA, and SUNRISE work toward improving health literacy, reducing behaviours associated with cancer risk, and maintaining high standards of care, all while addressing disparities in healthcare through telemedicine and remote monitoring, especially in rural and remote EU areas. Emphasizing the role of technology and innovation, they aim to advance patient-centered cancer prevention, using data and digital tools to enhance prevention efforts. Through targeted interventions and inclusive design, these projects focus on overcoming barriers to sustainable behavior change, contributing meaningfully to cancer prevention and overall public health improvement across Europe.

The Prevention and Early Detection Cluster is an example of the collaborative approach uniting EU-funded projects that focus on cancer prevention. Through this collective effort, the Cluster aims to address shared challenges and strategies, promote best practices, and accelerate progress towards reducing cancer risk across Europe. Aligned with the European Union's Mission on Cancer, the Cluster plays a key role in contributing to the prevention objectives set by the mission. The EU Mission on Cancer seeks to improve the lives of over 3 million people by 2030, focusing on prevention, treatment, and support for those affected by cancer, including their families. One of the primary goals of the mission is to foster sustainable behavioural change that reduces cancer risk. This includes encouraging healthier lifestyles through improved diets, increased physical activity, and reduced smoking. However, achieving such behavioural change is complex, influenced by various factors at both individual and systemic levels. It requires coordinated efforts that integrate policy, tailored interventions, and supportive environments.

Three key projects are central to the Cluster: iBeChange, MELIORA, and SUNRISE. These projects work collectively to tackle the challenges associated with cancer prevention by promoting health literacy, addressing harmful behaviours, and ensuring high standards in cancer care. Specifically, iBeChange focuses on leveraging digital solutions and behavioural

interventions to encourage healthier lifestyles and reduce cancer risks; MELIORA is committed to empowering women at risk of breast cancer, as well as those currently facing the disease and survivors, by harnessing AI and digital tools to foster sustainable lifestyle changes; SUNRISE contributes by strengthening telemedicine and remote monitoring, with a particular focus on improving access to care in rural regions. Together, these projects harness cutting-edge technologies and data-driven approaches to drive patient-centred cancer prevention, creating a more equitable and effective system across the EU.

2.1 Projects in the Prevention & Early Detection-Behavioural Change Cluster

2.1.1 iBeChange

iBeChange

The iBeChange project aims to design, developing and test a platform – the iBeChange system that fosters behaviour change (BC) and emotional management (EM) to promote the adoption of healthy and sustainable habits to reduce cancer risk. Recognising the link between BC and EM, enhancing emotional skills will help increase the chance to adopt healthier lifestyles. The platform will specifically target European citizens at risk for lung, breast, and colorectal cancer, encouraging them to make lifestyle adjustments – such as improving their diet, increasing physical activity, reducing alcohol consumption, and quitting smoking – that can lower their cancer risk, by also addressing emotional well-being. Through AI-driven personalised interventions, iBeChange will deliver tailored support to users, tackling healthcare access disparities by providing remote expert guidance regardless of geographical location. Through the collaboration of clinical and technical professionals, as well as the integration of inputs from literature reviews, retrospective and public data, the iBeChange platform will be designed to align with Europe’s Beating Cancer Plan (EBCP). Overall, the project seeks to empower individuals to make informed lifestyle decisions, significantly contributing to cancer prevention and improving public health across Europe.

2.1.2 MELIORA

MELIORA Consortium (*Multimodal Engagement and sustainable Lifestyle Interventions Optimizing breast cancer Risk reduction supported by Artificial intelligence*) will jointly work with local actors at different levels for the realisation of eight (8) in total tailor-made lifestyle interventions and behavioural modification studies, including Artificial intelligence and digital tools, to promote sustainable behavioural changes among three target populations: i) healthy women at risk of developing breast cancer, ii) breast cancer patients and iii) breast cancer survivors. The MELIORA Virtual Coach interventions (VCIs) will take place across 4 different European countries (Greece, Sweden, Spain and Lithuania) and 6 piloting centers targeting 2000 women in urban and rural areas including participants throughout the socioeconomic spectrum. Primary health care centers, hospitals or patients'/survivors' organisations will be used as entry points to the community. The goal of the MELIORA VCIs is to evaluate the effect of multiple individual and contextual factors on the uptake and sustainability of behavioural changes. At the same time, specific bottlenecks and barriers that prevent the uptake of sustainable behavioural change will be identified to support the development of optimal approaches for reaching and involving disadvantaged socio-economic population groups and people living in rural areas and will provide best practices for the wider intervention's uptake and scale-up. Based on the effectiveness, health economic evaluation and budget impact analysis of the MELIORA VCIs, national and European stakeholders will be invited to co-

creation workshops aiming to evaluate the potential for adoption of the MELIORA VCIs in other regions or countries in Europe.

2.1.3 SUNRISE

The SUNRISE project aims to co-create, implement and evaluate an innovative digitally enhanced life-skills programme for primary prevention of cancer through sustainable health behaviour change in adolescents. Primary prevention of cancer through behaviour changes in adolescence, a critical period in which many risk behaviours are initiated, is a significant health and societal challenge in Europe. To tackle the health and societal challenge of primary prevention of cancer in Europe, SUNRISE will combine an established, evidence-based digital solution for smoking prevention, with novel intervention approaches such as peer social media campaigns, advertising literacy training, educational games, and social robot platforms, to take cancer prevention approaches for adolescents in the EU to the next level. The digitally enhanced programme will be developed through co-creation with schools-as-living-labs methods involving multiple societal actors such as educators, adolescents, parents, public health experts, and policy-makers. The programme will be implemented and evaluated at large scale across 154 schools and 7500 students in urban and rural regions of 8 European countries, including socially disadvantaged groups and ethnic minorities. Overall, the SUNRISE project aims to revolutionize primary cancer prevention in Europe by fostering sustainable, large-scale behavioural change in adolescents through an inclusive, digitally enhanced and evidence-based approach.

3. The Prevention and Early Detection (Behavioural Change) Cluster

The Prevention and Early Detection (Behavioural Change) Cluster aims to address cancer-related challenges through collaborative and coordinated approaches that engage the public, policymakers, healthcare professionals, industry, educators, and media. The collaboration is

designed to create an environment that fosters sustainable behavioral changes essential for cancer prevention. By aligning efforts across the iBeChange, MELIORA, and SUNRISE projects, the Cluster coordinates expertise from diverse stakeholders to minimize duplicative efforts, identify shared obstacles, expand reach, and share best practices. The Cluster focuses on enhancing health promotion and cancer prevention programs by raising awareness about behavioral risk factors. Through this unified approach, resources, knowledge, and expertise are pooled to maximize impact, particularly across different regions, socioeconomic levels, and vulnerable groups. This aligns directly with the Horizon Europe Work Programme, which emphasizes primary cancer prevention through sustainable behavioural change. Expected outcomes include targeted health promotion, accessible recommendations and support programs, and policy engagement to create supportive, healthy environments.

In other words, the Cluster’s scientific collaboration plan outlines a practical framework for facilitating coordinated efforts while adapting to evolving challenges. Collaboration tools include a shared digital workspace for data and document sharing, designated contact points, and milestone tracking to ensure goal alignment and resource efficiency. Best practices are continuously identified, evaluated, and integrated to ensure high-quality, evidence-based interventions that can be replicated across diverse social and geographical contexts.

Annual meetings allow project partners to assess progress, address challenges, and adjust strategies as needed, fostering trust and reinforcing the collective vision. Recognizing potential risks, the Cluster employs a proactive risk management strategy to address challenges such as resource limitations, stakeholder conflicts, and the complex nature of driving behavioral change. This strategy aims to mitigate uncertainties and enhance the Cluster’s ability to achieve its objectives effectively, ensuring the success and sustainability of its cancer prevention efforts.

Table 1: Risk and Mitigation Action

Risk	Mitigation action
Challenges with shared digital workspaces	Establish clear guidelines for file sharing, version control, and workspace navigation.
Conflict	Create a conflict resolution framework, and promote an open, transparent dialogue among all partners.
Divergent stakeholder objectives	Regularly consult with stakeholders to align expectations.

Failure to adhere to project timelines.	Implement a detailed timeline with milestone tracking and conduct regular progress reviews to identify delays early and adjust planning accordingly.
Ineffective communication	Establish clear communication protocols, appoint communication leads. Contact points, and ensure minutes are shared after meetings.
Misalignment among partners	Establish regular communication channels, create clear and shared objectives, and hold alignment meetings early in the timeline of the Cluster.

4. Strands of Cluster work

4.1 Research and Innovation

4.1.1 Strand goals and participants

This strand aims to foster scientific advancement in cancer prevention and early detection by harmonizing research methods, reducing overlaps, and creating synergies across the cluster projects. It encourages collaborative work, allowing projects to share resources, best practices, and insights to enhance research outcomes, formulate policy recommendations, and support sustainable behavioural change.

The SUNRISE project leads this strand, collaborating with key institutions across various projects, including iBeChange, MELIORA, and several European health organizations. These organizations work in a structured framework with shared responsibilities to drive research and innovation.

Table 2: Overview of Organisations Participating in the Research and Innovation Strand

Project	Partner
iBeChange	European Institute of Oncology (IEO)
	European Alliance for Personalized Medicine (EAPM)
MELIORA	Harakopio University of Athens (HUA)
	European Health Management Association (EHMA)
SUNRISE (lead)	PredictBy (PBY)
	Institutul Oncologic Prof Dr Ion Chiricuta Cluj-Napoca (IOCN)

	Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH)
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4.2 Citizen Engagement

4.2.1 Strand Goals and Participants

The Citizen Engagement strand focuses on involving patients and the public in the Cluster's projects to ensure research and interventions align with real-world needs. This approach bridges scientific research with societal impact, improving the relevance, accessibility, and acceptability of cancer prevention solutions. By incorporating patients' experiences, the strand empowers individuals to shape interventions, enhancing both scientific and societal outcomes.

The MELIORA project leads the Citizen Engagement strand, with collaboration from several organizations across iBeChange, MELIORA, and SUNRISE projects, including European health-focused institutions and patient associations. (See Table 5 for details.)

Table 3: Overview of Organisations Participating in the Citizen Engagement Strand

Project	Partner
iBeChange	European Institute of Oncology (IEO)
	European Alliance for Personalized Medicine (EAPM)
MELIORA (lead)	Harakopio University of Athens (HUA)
	European Health Management Association (EHMA)
	PredictyBy (PBY)
SUNRISE	Cyprus Association of Cancer Patients and Friends (PASYKAF)

Table 4: Overview of Foreseen Workshops and Other Related Citizen Engagement-Related Activities Per Project

iBeChange	In the iBeChange project, activities related to citizens engagement play a crucial role and involve a series of tasks focused on actively involving citizens. In order to develop an effective and engaging platform fostering behavioural change and emotional management, participatory co-design principles and practices will be applied, ensuring that citizens are involved in every phase of the eHealth technology design process. To achieve this, a key activity involving citizen participation will be the organization of focus group discussions with individuals in at-risk age groups for breast, lung, and colorectal cancer. Citizens
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	<p>will be recruited in Italy, Spain, and Romania, for a total of 60-96 participants. The focus group discussions will aim to: collecting information and direct feedback on specific health and prevention issues; understanding the challenges and barriers that citizens face in accessing and adhering to prevention and screening programs; identifying critical areas where informational resources can be improved for this specific population. Overall, these focus group discussions may also reveal new issues that were not previously identified by researchers, contributing to further project improvements and informing about the relationship between health behaviors and technologies. Furthermore, for the Evaluation of Prevention Policy Strategies that will be led by the European Alliance for Personalized Medicine (EAPM), citizens will be invited to participate in expert panels to evaluate prevention and screening strategies. Using Big Data, past policies will be analyzed, and citizen participation will allow the exploration and understanding of: opinions and attitudes towards prevention and screening; the reasons for acceptance or refusal of prevention programs; the barriers to participation.</p>
MELIORA	<p>Between June and September 2024, MELIORA organized 5 workshops with patients, breast cancer survivors and women at risk, to study the barriers and factors that could facilitate breast cancer prevention interventions in Spain, Sweden, Lithuania, Greece and at the European level. They helped to identify end-users' health needs, their intention and readiness to adopt the MELIORA solution. Furthermore, patients will be gathered from all participating countries to evaluate the MELIORA Virtual Coach from the patient perspective, ensuring that it is user-friendly, effective, and meets their needs. This hands-on testing ensures that the digital health technologies we develop are both practical and responsive to the lived experiences of patients.</p>
SUNRISE	<p>Within the framework of the SUNRISE project and the contribution to the citizen engagement, it is expected that the projects involved in the cluster, should organize exchanges with citizens, including patients, to engage them and to address their views. In this regard, the SUNRISE has until now organized: 5 working groups, i.e. "Councils", with adolescents, parents, educators, public health experts, and local policy-makers have been established, a large cross-sectional survey with adolescents across all 8 countries to assess (digital) health literacy, cancer literacy, cancer risk</p>

	behaviors and environmental factors, an online survey with adolescents, parents, and educators to elicit digital tools requirements, a plenary workshop on socio-technical scenarios of the utilization and sustainability of the programme and the 1st round of co-creation activities has started with 4 workshops on co-creation methodologies and SUNRISE use cases have all been completed.
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Table 5: Overview of Each Project's External Advisory Bodies

iBeChange	The External Advisory Board (EAB) was established at the beginning of the project and includes patient associations. This board meets every six months, and the first meeting was held on July 30, 2024. The meeting served as an opportunity to update the board on the activities undertaken and those currently in progress within the iBeChange project. Additionally, it aimed to gather feedback from the board to ensure their support and facilitate their consultative function. The patient associations included in the EAB are the following: European Cancer Breast Coalition (Europa Donna), Lung Cancer Europe (LuCe), Digestive Cancer Europe (DiCE). Further, in the EAB are also involved Joseph Maria Borrás (Director Plan of Oncology - Spain) and UO Prevention Members of Regione Lombardia (Italy). Additionally, iBeChange consortium has appointed a Public Health Policy Advisory Committee (PAC) which will be instrumental in ensuring that the project is not only patient-centered but also aligned with broader healthcare and policy objectives, by fostering open dialogue and connections with key stakeholders.
MELIORA	The SPAB (European Stakeholder and Policy Advisory Board) was created in the beginning of 2024, with a first meeting taking place on September 10th, 2024. The participants of this meeting included individuals who represented Cancer Patients Europe, the Champalimaud Foundation, the Clinical Hospital Centre Rijeka, the Turku University of Applied Sciences, and the Greek Institute of Information Technology and Communications. At least one meeting per year will be organized for consultation, as well as ad hoc meetings and individual consultations upon needs.
SUNRISE	The independent Ethics Advisory Committee (EAC) in SUNRISE has been established. The EAC is composed of 3 independent experts, and aims at the monitoring of any ethical, regulatory, or psychosocial concerns related to the

	implementation of the SUNRISE activities. Regular meetings take place every 3 months.
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4.3 Addressing Inequalities in Access to Quality Care

This strand aims to understand and reduce inequalities in cancer care access, which are often embedded in social, economic, and political systems. Focusing on sustainable behavioural changes to reduce cancer risk, the projects will use tools like the ECIR data tool to analyse disparities in cancer prevention across Europe. Activities include co-creation workshops, focus groups, and policy evaluation with different European countries (Italy, Spain, Romania, Sweden, Greece, and others) piloting interventions.

Table 6: Domain, target group, and pilot countries per project

Project	Domain	Target Group	Pilot Countries
IBeChange	-Socio-economic status -Education -Country of origin and residence - Digital literacy	European citizens at risk of breast, colorectal, and lung cancer	-Italy -Spain -Romania
MELIORA	-Education -Income -Urbanization -Digital literacy	-Healthy women at risk -Breast cancer patients -Breast cancer survivors	-Sweden -Lithuania -Greece -Spain
SUNRISE	-Education -Country -Digital literacy	-Adolescents, parents, educators	-Greece -Switzerland -Slovenia -Spain -Cyprus -Italy -Belgium -Romania

4.3.1 Strand goals and participants

The MELIORA project leads this effort, with participation from iBeChange (European Institute of Oncology) and SUNRISE (Centre for Research & Technology Hellas, Cyprus Association of Cancer Patients and Friends).

Table 7: Overview of Organisations participating in the Addressing Inequalities Strand

Project	Organization
IBeChange	❖ European Institute of Oncology (IEO)
MELIORA (lead)	PredictBy (PBY)
	Harokopio University of Athens (HUA)
SUNRISE	Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH)
	Cyprus Association of Cancer Patients and Friends (PASYKAF)

4.4 Communication and Dissemination

4.4.1 Strand Goals and Participants

The **Communication and Dissemination strand** in the Prevention Cluster aims to maximize outreach to key stakeholders (policymakers, healthcare professionals, patient organizations, and the public) by promoting developments and fostering collaboration across the iBeChange, MELIORA, and SUNRISE consortia. By uniting strengths, this strand enhances visibility and supports cancer prevention efforts through knowledge sharing and engagement.

This strand is led by the **iBeChange** consortium with support from the **European Alliance for Personalized Medicine (EAPM)**. Contributors include partners from all three consortia.

Table 8: Overview of Organizations Participating in the Communication and Dissemination Strand

Project	Partner
IBeChange (lead)	European Institute of Oncology (IEO)
	European Alliance for Personalized Medicine (EAPM)
MELIORA	European Health Management Association (EHMA)
SUNRISE	Cyprus Association of Cancer Patients and Friends (PASYKAF)

5. Cluster annual meetings

Cluster annual meetings serve as a platform for project partners to review progress, share insights, and plan future common scientific activities. They also offer an opportunity to align strategic priorities, address emerging trends, and anticipate challenges. By fostering an environment of trust and cooperation, these meetings reinforce the shared vision and commitment of all partners involved in the Cluster. Four annual meetings are scheduled during the Cluster's duration (M12, M24, M36, M48). Each meeting will be organised by one of the participating projects, which will be responsible for preparing the agenda and drafting conclusions. As the projects have varying durations, the Cluster will conclude when the shortest project, i.e. MELIORA, ends (M48). Meetings will be organised on a rotational basis, potentially linked to other relevant events or each project's annual meeting to optimise resources. Meetings can be held in person, hybrid, or in fully remote formats and periodic virtual meetings are recommended to strengthen collaboration. Typically, the annual meetings will be half-day or full-day events, depending on the agenda. This deliverable provides a report of the first annual cluster meeting, highlighting the key discussions and outlining the collaborative efforts of iBeChange, MELIORA, and SUNRISE within the Prevention and Early Detection Cluster. It also summaries the action points that emerged during the meeting.

5.1 First annual cluster meeting

During the Cluster kick-off meeting on 6th March 2024, it was suggested that the first Cluster meeting be held around the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) Congress in Barcelona (13-17th September 2024). In line with this suggestion, the first meeting was hosted by iBeChange, which, to ensure efficient use of resources, decided to hold its annual project meeting in Barcelona on 17-18th September 2024 and to organise the annual Cluster meeting on the same occasion.

The meeting started with an overview of the research updates from the three projects, followed by progress updates on the cluster activities. A specific session was dedicated to the annual policy recommendations: this included a round table for discussion on planned activities and mitigation strategies for the potential gaps in their deployment. A broad overview of the meeting agenda can be found in the Appendix 1.

The meeting participation was allowed in both in person and online format, to ensure broad participation to discussion and ensure collaboration effectiveness. The participants list can be found in Appendix 2.

Laura Garcia Ibanez (LGI) – representing the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA) - introduced the annual Cluster meeting with an overview of the European Cancer Mission, highlighting its main goal: to improve the lives of more than 3 million people by 2030 through prevention, treatment, and support for those affected by cancer, including their families, enabling them to live longer and healthier lives. This is in alignment with Europe’s Beating Cancer Plan. The mission is built around four interconnected objectives: understanding cancer, prevention and early detection, diagnosis and treatment, and improving the quality of life for those affected by cancer, including their families. LGI described the mission as a portfolio of cross-disciplinary actions aimed at achieving a bold, inspirational, and measurable goal within a defined timeframe, with significant societal and policy impact, relevant to a large segment of the European population. The Cancer Mission aligns with several EU policies and initiatives, including local and legislative frameworks. LGI emphasised the connection between the EU Cancer Mission and Horizon Europe initiatives. The mission’s Work Programme 2021-2022-2023 encompasses 50 projects across 8 clusters, one of which is the Prevention and Early Detection Cluster, which aims to enhance cancer prevention for EU citizens through specific actions such as: Developing new methods and technologies for screening and early prediction; conducting implementation research to improve cancer prevention programs; establishing a one-stop cancer information centre on prevention (an evidence-clearing house to assist Member States in implementing effective cancer prevention strategies); Boosting research and innovation into risk assessment; optimizing access to screening.

One of the key objectives is to establish synergies in prevention with other EU missions, as actions under different missions will support cancer prevention. LGI mentioned the general activities to be undertaken collaboratively, including the organisation of the 2nd (2025), 3rd (2026), and 4th (2027) annual meetings. Additionally, she highlighted that an annual update under the Citizen Engagement and Addressing inequalities strand, is required and should be included in the meeting conclusions.

Finally, LGI presented a table outlining the progress of key deliverables:

The meeting started with an overview of the research updates from the three projects, followed by progress updates on the cluster activities. A specific session was dedicated to the annual policy recommendations: this included a round table for discussion on planned activities and mitigation.

- DMP with a common chapter on the cluster • M6 (summer 2024) – pending;
- Common deliverable on Scientific Collaboration • 30 Sept 2024; - completed;
- Common Video and/or Brochure • 30 Nov 2024;
- 1st Annual Meeting Report 30 Nov 2024
- Chapter on Citizen Engagement /Inequalities/R&I collaboration;
- 1st Policy Brief R&I Strand • 30 Nov 2024.

6. Research updates from the cluster projects

6.1 SUNRISE

Kostantinos Votis and Andreas Triantafyllidis presented the SUNRISE project. The SUNRISE project aims to co-create, implement, and evaluate an innovative, digitally enhanced life-skills program for the primary prevention of cancer through sustainable health behaviour change in adolescents. The program will be tailored to adolescents' socio-economic, cultural, and environmental diversities, with a noticeable impact on society at large. This project includes 19 partners from 11 countries, providing multidisciplinary expertise in cancer prevention, public health, eHealth, health behaviour change, psychology, digital technologies, data management, social innovation, biomedical ethics, and large-scale implementation studies. The main challenges identified include the significant gap in achieving effective and sustainable health behavior changes among adolescents for primary cancer prevention. These challenges stem from: a lack of systematic pathways to deliver digital health interventions for adolescents; the massive investment of time required by educators to prepare and administer such programs; difficulty in maintaining student engagement; difficulty in adapting intervention materials to fit the diversity of children's backgrounds.

The main objectives of SUNRISE include:

- ❖ Co-create with school-as-a-living-lab methods a novel and highly engaging digitally-enhanced program for primary prevention of cancer through sustainable health behaviour change in adolescents, tailored to socio-economic, cultural and environmental diversities (urban and rural) in 8 European countries (Greece, Switzerland, Slovenia, Spain, Cyprus, Italy, Belgium, Romania), to have tangible impact on the society and socially disadvantaged populations at large (WP1).

- This will involve 5 working groups (n=40), i.e. “Councils”, with adolescents, parents, educators, public health experts, and local policymakers; a large cross-sectional survey with adolescents (n=5000) across all 8 countries to assess (digital) health literacy, cancer literacy, cancer risk behaviours, and environmental factors, including >20% migrants and ethnic minorities; an online survey with adolescents, parents, and educators (n=500), to elicit digital tools requirements; and a plenary workshop on technical scenarios for the utilization and sustainability of the program. The first round of co-creation activities has started.

- ❖ Explore, monitor, and assess cancer prevention knowledge systematically and continuously identify unmet needs, barriers and facilitators for the sustainable implementation of the digitally enhanced cancer prevention program (WP2).
 - This includes an inventory of evidence-based cancer prevention strategies; a repository of persuasive multimedia content; and three literature reviews on a) factors influencing adherence to digital health programs in adolescents; b) effective and sustainable digital health behaviour change techniques; and c) successful implementation strategies for digital health interventions with potential impact on reducing health inequalities.

- ❖ Develop and use interactive digital tools for the improvement, tailoring and scaling-up of evidence-based and novel interventions toward the life-skills training of adolescents (WP3).
 - This will include: improving the ISGF SmartCoach evidence-based life-skills digital intervention through the addition of persuasive multimedia content tailored to cultural specifics, ready for use in the 8 countries; a novel social media influencer campaign to promote healthy diet behaviours; promotion of ECAC and preventive behaviours for cancer through interactions with a social bot platform; educational games for advertising and health literacy training for the 8 countries; an interactive health education module for adolescents, parents, and educators; and a tailored digital platform with authoring and monitoring tools for the intervention program.

Shared key points from the Plenary Session

-TU/e (iBeChange) expressed interest in exploring the possibility of sharing educational materials, recognizing that the ideas promoted by both **iBeChange** and **SUNRISE** align closely. The primary objective of both projects is to improve cancer prevention, which can be significantly advanced through the dissemination of digital educational resources.

-**SUNRISE** acknowledged the importance of this collaboration, emphasizing that their project adheres to an open-science approach sharing methodologies and materials.

6.2 MELIORA

Niki Morouti (NM) chaired this session and presented the main aim of the MELIORA project, which is to promote sustainable behavioural changes among healthy women at risk of developing breast cancer, breast cancer patients, and breast cancer survivors. This will be implemented through eight tailor-made lifestyle and behavioural modification interventions, with the engagement of local actors. A second principal aim is to assess the scalability and transferability of these interventions to other countries or regions in Europe.

The MELIORA project is structured into eight work packages (WPs). Under WP3, the project has nearly completed the identification of current policies, legislation, regulatory procedures, services, and environmental characteristics related to healthy eating, active living, and primary and secondary breast cancer care. A situation analysis report was created for the four implementation countries (Greece, Sweden, Spain, and Lithuania) in collaboration with engaged stakeholders. Workshops with citizens, breast cancer patients, breast cancer survivors, policymakers, and healthcare professionals have been organised in these countries.

NM also highlighted that the development of intervention materials is in progress, with the first draft set to be presented and discussed with the consortium in the upcoming consortium meeting (WP4). Additionally, the development of the MELIORA virtual coach is underway, and data collection campaigns (DCC) are scheduled to start in December 2024. Protocols for the DCC are expected to be finalised by the end of September 2024 (WP5). Work on tools for process, impact, and outcome evaluation is also ongoing (WP6). A key focus under WP7 is the design and implementation of eight tailor-made lifestyle and behavioural modification intervention studies, which will involve 2,080 participants across the four implementation countries. These will include healthy women at risk of breast cancer, breast cancer patients, and breast cancer survivors. The assessment of the process, impact evaluation, and cost-

effectiveness of the intervention is in progress, alongside a budget impact analysis and an assessment of the scalability of the MELIORA solution to other sites within the four countries.

NM concluded with updates on WP8, particularly on recommendations and dissemination activities. The establishment of a "European Stakeholder and Policy Advisory Board" has taken place (first meeting on September 10th, 2024), and the MELIORA website was launched (M04), alongside the release of the first newsletter (M06). Additionally, a video and/or cluster brochure is currently being developed.

An Ethics Advisory Board (EAB) has also been established in accordance with ethical requirements to oversee processes under the various WPs.

Shared key points from the Plenary Session

-TU/e (iBeChange) proposed that the knowledge generated across various projects could be utilized to identify connections in the technology being employed. This collaborative approach aims to enhance the efficacy of the virtual coaching platform by integrating insights and methodologies from multiple sources. The discussions reflect a strategic approach to the development of the virtual coaching platform, emphasizing behavioral modification for healthy women and survivors while excluding genetic factors.

-The collaborative sharing of knowledge across projects is expected to enhance the platform's technological foundation and overall effectiveness.

-Next Steps should be based to explore opportunities for collaboration across projects to identify and integrate technological connections, and to define risk factors relevant to cancer patients and survivors.

6.3 IBeChange

Gabriella Pravettoni (Principal Investigator; PI) and Marianna Masiero (MM) (Co-PI) chaired the session. The PI introduced the iBeChange consortium, listing all the partners involved and outlining the project's main goals.

The iBeChange PI and Co-PI presented an infographic summarising the project's specific workflows and achievements, emphasising dissemination, as this is critical in translating research goals into tangible outcomes.

MM then outlined specific activities performed by iBeChange Consortium from December 2023 to September 2024 across various research levels:

Table 9: IBeChange- Activities Performed M1-9

Area	Actions	Related WP/Deliverable
Clinical	Literature reviews on behavioural and psycho-social risk factors.	❖ WP2 ❖ D2.1
	Co-design studies & user driven approach	❖ WP2
	Identification of evidence-based interventions	❖ WP2
	Definition of user journey	❖ WP2 ❖ WP3 ❖ WP4
	Health Habit Score	❖ WP2
	Education Contents	❖ WP2 ❖ WP3
	Discussion of clinical study protocols	❖ WP5
Technical level	Preliminary app design	❖ WP4
	Comprehensive research on wearables	❖ WP3
	Research on implementation of the recommender system	❖ WP4
	Retrospective data collection on colorectal and lung cancer patients	❖ WP3
Ethical level	Appointment of the Independent Ethics Advisory Board (IEAB)	❖ WP9
	Foundation of the Data Management Plan (DMP) and Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA).	❖ WP7
Dissemination level	Development of the project website	❖ WP8 ❖ D8.7
	Creation of an extranet	❖ WP8

		❖ D8.7
	Issuance of a press release	❖ WP8
	Newsletter updates	❖ WP8
	Social Media Activity	❖ WP8
	Production of project videos	❖ WP8

MM also highlighted how iBeChange has integrated the cluster activities with the life circle of the project. In particular, the following activities has been performed:

- ❖ **Addressing inequalities (Lead: MELIORA):** iBeChange has participated in joint meetings aimed at identifying common variables, methodologies, and potential challenges for establishing best practices.
- ❖ Furthermore, iBeChange has completed a scoping review identifying some specific variables, such as social support and socio-economic status, related to inequalities in healthcare on which cluster might work in the future producing a common scientific publication.
- ❖ **Communication and dissemination (Lead: iBeChange):** iBeChange is leading the communication and dissemination strand, supported by EAPM and eCancer. This has involved coordinating the organisation of the first annual cluster meeting and developing a Google Drive platform for collaborative work. Additionally, the first draft of Deliverable “Common work plan for scientific collaboration under the “Prevention & Early Detection (Behavioural Change)” cluster”, focused on the common scientific work plan, has been prepared, and partner contributions are ongoing.
- ❖ **Data management:** There is no designated leader, but several partners, including I-HD (the ethical partner of iBeChange), have expressed interest in contributing. A suggestion for co-leadership among projects has been raised, but this requires further discussion.

MM concluded by providing an overview of the upcoming deadlines for drafting and submitting the Common work plan for scientific collaboration under the “Prevention & Early Detection (Behavioural Change)” cluster that was agreed by the involved colleagues.

Shared key points from the Plenary Session

-SUNRISE suggested further investigations to identify commonalities among the three ongoing projects. This step is intended to facilitate the development of a cohesive research cluster, enhancing collaboration and resource sharing.

-SUNRISE inquired about the age range for study participants. iBeChange clarified that the clinical studies are still in the design phase, and the age range will be determined based on periods of highest cancer risk. The systematic review will concentrate on the adult population aged 20 and older. While age is the main risk factor for colorectal and lung cancer, sex is also significant for breast cancer, which predominantly affects females.

-Further discussions with SUNRISE focused on the specific risk factors being considered for integration into the SUNRISE project. iBeChange agreed with this approach, indicating it would aid in the identification of various datasets and common subjects.

7. Policy recommendations

The aim of this chapter is to present initial policy recommendations that have resulted from the annual cluster meeting of the Prevention and Early Detection Cluster, which was held in Barcelona, Spain, on September 17th, 2024. This cluster was created under the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and includes three projects- iBeChange, MELIORA, and SUNRISE- which are focused on the development of innovative strategies for cancer prevention and early detection. This part will outline the policy recommendations from each project, provide an overview of the process that led to their development, identify common overarching policy themes, and present an assessment of the recommendations' potential impact.

This session was chaired by Denis Horgan (iBeChange) and consisted of a collaborative discussion, guided by the following questions:

- ❖ SWOT Analysis of how they are tackling Prevention
- ❖ What are the gaps and how to mitigate these?
- ❖ How to ensure uptake in healthcare systems?
- ❖ What are the policy enablers to facilitate this?
- ❖ Common elements that the EU should take

- ❖ Specific elements for LMIC, and minority groups

7.1 SUNRISE

7.1.1 Annual Cluster Summary

Adela Maghear (AM, IOCN, SUNRISE) representing the SUNRISE team explained that the idea behind the dissemination effort at a policy level relies on the assumption that, at the EU level, there is a large availability of resources in the field of health research. Those resources should not only remain as scientific articles and websites but should be translated into a format that is relevant for policymakers: scientific results should be converted into meaningful measures.

In this context, the European Commission should be considered the legislative body, and the role of the Cancer Mission is not just to bring innovation to the EU citizens, but also to impact policy-making. Research outcomes can be translated into meaningful policy data through the following steps:

- ❖ Develop a policy strategy that effectively communicates the project's research outcomes, their impact, and regulatory relevance to policymakers at both the EU and national levels.
- ❖ Raise awareness about the project among a broader audience, including policymakers (EU institutions, national legislators), patient and healthcare professional organisations, academia, national health authorities, industry, and civil society.
- ❖ Enable policy dialogue between research partners and policymakers (EU institutions, national legislators) to inform and drive policy change.

To achieve these goals, it is essential to establish engagement with relevant policymakers. This includes identifying key figures at both the EU and national levels to collaboratively define the most efficient means of communicating the policy implications of the research outcomes. Relevant stakeholders include European Parliament Members (MEPs from the ENVI/SANT committee), the EU Commission (cabinet and directorate general levels), Member States (health ministries and health authorities), and the EU Council (health attachés from upcoming presidencies such as Poland, Denmark, Cyprus, etc.). From a practical standpoint, strategies to translate research outcomes into meaningful policy data include the production of policy brochures and reports that incorporate relevant research outcomes tailored for policymakers, as well as creating synergies with existing and ongoing legislative and non-

legislative acts and initiatives. Additionally, it is recommended that all policy materials include recommendations aimed at suggesting feasible ways to apply the research outcomes in policy development. To reach a larger audience and raise awareness about the project and its policy impact at the national level, the projects should consider translating materials into multiple EU languages.

In summary, the primary aim of researchers in establishing contact with relevant policymakers is to open a dialogue with them from the very start of project implementation. Involving all project partners in evidence-based discussions, workshops, and consultations with policymakers could be beneficial, as well as organising periodic meetings and online calls to discuss the progress of research activities and their expected results. It is also fundamental to organise events and utilise social media to engage stakeholders. The SUNRISE project suggests organising at least two one-day events in Brussels within the EU Parliament/Commission: one aimed at introducing the project and its policy implications, and the other focused on discussing implementation progress and the challenges encountered along the way.

The main take-aways for policy-makers were summarized as follows:

- ❖ To enhance accessibility and inclusivity in preventive healthcare, it is crucial to support socioeconomically disadvantaged populations, particularly in remote and underserved areas of the EU.
- ❖ Harmonizing preventive policies across regions is vital to prevent fragmented healthcare approaches and ensure effective implementation.
- ❖ Structured reimbursement models that prioritize preventive services are key to shifting healthcare from reactive to preventive care.
- ❖ Integrating mental health into prevention frameworks is essential for a holistic healthcare approach.
- ❖ As digital health initiatives and data-sharing expand, prioritizing data privacy and cybersecurity is crucial.
- ❖ Expanding public health campaigns to promote lifestyle changes is vital for raising awareness and fostering healthier behaviors.
- ❖ Collaborative frameworks are essential for supporting research and innovation, which are key to enhancing preventive measures.
- ❖ Fostering multistakeholder collaboration is crucial for effective cancer prevention policy change, aligning diverse perspectives and resources towards a common goal.

Shared key points from the Plenary Session

All meeting participants agreed that the primary focus of collaborative work in this strand is to establish a general yet clear understanding of where projects should invest in delivering policy recommendations—such as the creation of educational materials, events, and social media campaigns—to optimise alignment among them. In particular, opportunities should be identified with a focus on the research and innovation sector.

HADEA reinforced the message that projects do not need to reinvent themselves or their objectives for the sake of collaboration; the EU has already established channels for communication with policy officers. Laura Garcia Ibanez can be utilised as a resource to enhance this communication avenue.

7.1.2 Annual Policy Recommendations

Strengthening accessibility and inclusivity in preventive healthcare

To strengthen accessibility and inclusivity in preventive healthcare, it is essential to support socioeconomically disadvantaged populations, especially in remote and underserved EU regions. The iBeChange, MELIORA, and SUNRISE projects emphasize making preventive tools accessible through subsidized AI-driven and telehealth solutions that maintain privacy standards while catering to diverse demographics. Digital literacy programs should be region-specific, ensuring that all communities, including vulnerable groups, can engage with these health technologies effectively. By incorporating feedback from the projects' citizen engagement activities, these initiatives can remain user-centred, accommodating the needs and challenges of various populations. Additionally, preventive health communications and digital tools must be tailored to respect linguistic and cultural differences across regions. This approach builds on SUNRISE's focus on engaging adolescents and families in different cultural contexts, fostering higher acceptance and engagement.

Harmonizing preventive policy measures across regions

Harmonizing preventive policies across regions to avoid fragmented healthcare approaches is crucial to ensure effective implementation. Member States need further support to adapt EU-wide policy frameworks to their national healthcare systems while fostering standard preventive practices. This approach mirrors the collaborative framework within the Prevention and Early Detection Cluster, which establishes cross-national work plans for cohesive cancer prevention and behavioural change efforts. Furthermore, cross-national data-sharing agreements should promote secure and ethical data exchanges, supporting

preventive healthcare research. These protocols must comply with GDPR and align with the objectives of the upcoming European Health Data Space (EHDS). Transparency is key to uphold patient trust, in line with the Cluster's data management and security practices.

Incentivizing preventive care over reactive care

Structured reimbursement models that prioritize preventive services are important pillars that could shift healthcare models from reactive to preventive care. These frameworks should align with the preventive approach championed by the Cluster, making early detection and behavioural change interventions financially viable for healthcare providers. Investment in prevention research and technologies, particularly digital solutions like MELIORA's Virtual Coach, should be incentivized. This will ensure that companies and academic/research institutions can focus on developing tools that facilitate behavioural change, especially for at-risk groups, thereby advancing patient-centred care.

Integrating mental health in prevention frameworks

Integrating mental health into prevention frameworks is essential to provide a holistic approach to healthcare, recognizing that mental well-being significantly influences physical health. Mental health support should be integrated within cancer prevention programs at national level, as highlighted in the initiatives of the SUNRISE project. By including psychological services in preventive health packages, healthcare providers can better support high-risk populations, especially cancer survivors and those navigating the emotional challenges associated with cancer or cancer stigma. The Cluster's projects underscore the importance of engaging users in co-creation activities and workshops, which allows for mental health services and preventive measures to be shaped by real user experiences, making them more relevant and adaptable.

Addressing data privacy and cybersecurity concerns

Addressing data privacy and cybersecurity is paramount as digital health initiatives and data-sharing practices expand. Stringent data security policies should be enacted to protect sensitive patient information, echoing the Prevention Cluster's data management framework. Clear, user-centred consent mechanisms that inform individuals about data collection, usage, and sharing practices can foster patient trust. This aligns with the Cluster's shared data governance protocols, which prioritize ethical data practices and transparency.

Expanding public health campaigns to prevent health risks

Expanding public health campaigns to promote lifestyle changes that can prevent health risk is essential to raise awareness and encourage healthier behaviours. Drawing on insights from iBeChange's and MELIORA's citizen engagement workshops, there is a need for campaigns at the national level to educate the public about modifiable risk factors, such as lifestyle choices affecting cancer risk, while supporting the EU Cancer Mission's overarching goals. Local initiatives targeting high-risk groups should be encouraged by employing SUNRISE's model of community engagement to promote behavioural change at the community level. This approach not only resonates with the needs of diverse population groups but also leverages local partnerships to ensure sustainable lifestyle changes.

Supporting research and innovation through collaborative frameworks

Research and innovation play a central role in the effectiveness and sustainability of preventive measures. Supporting cross-project research funding and shared resources aligns with the goals of the collaborative framework of the Prevention and Early Detection Cluster, allowing for optimized resources use and impactful research outcomes. Policies that encourage patient and citizen involvement in research ensure that interventions reflect real-world needs. The iBeChange and SUNRISE projects emphasize citizen engagement, which enables the development of interventions tailored to the lived experiences and preferences of those they serve, enhancing the scientific and societal relevance of preventive strategies.

Fostering multistakeholder collaboration to drive the policy change

Fostering multistakeholder collaboration is essential for driving effective policy change in cancer prevention, as it unites diverse perspectives and resources towards a common goal. Engaging stakeholders—including healthcare professionals, policymakers, researchers, patient advocacy groups, and community organizations—ensures that varied expertise and experiences inform the development and implementation of comprehensive prevention strategies. By creating platforms for dialogue and partnership, stakeholders can identify barriers to effective cancer prevention, share best practices, and advocate for evidence-based policies that prioritize public health. Such collaborative efforts not only enhance the legitimacy and acceptance of policy initiatives but also mobilize broader community support, ultimately leading to sustained improvements in cancer prevention outcomes. These policy recommendations, tailored to align with the Cluster's objectives and the EU Cancer Mission, reinforce the collaborative model pursued by iBeChange, MELIORA, and SUNRISE. Through integrated policies, accessible tools, and citizen-driven research, these initiatives aim to reduce cancer incidence and foster healthier lifestyles across Europe.

Table 10: Key Policy Actions for Advancing Preventive Healthcare Initiatives

Policy area	Key actions
Accessibility and inclusivity	Subsidized AI and telehealth solutions; region-specific digital literacy programs
Harmonizing guidelines	EU-wide adaptable frameworks; secure cross-national data-sharing agreements
Incentivizing preventive care	Reimbursement models for preventive services; investment incentives for prevention research and technologies
Integrating mental health	Integrating psychological services in prevention packages; co-creation with user input
Data privacy and cybersecurity	Stringent data protection policies; user-friendly consent mechanisms
Public health campaigns	Campaigns on modifiable risk factors; community initiatives targeting high-risk groups
Supporting research and innovation	Cross-project funding; policies co-created with patients and the general public
Fostering multistakeholder collaboration to drive the policy change.	Engaging diverse stakeholders; creating platforms for dialogue and partnership

7.2 MELIORA

7.2.1 Annual Cluster Summary

Dolores Cviticanin (DC), policy officer at EHMA, chaired this session and introduced it with a brief overview of the MELIORA Project.

Recognising that breast cancer represents a significant social and economic challenge—having the highest treatment costs of any cancer and with projections indicating that the number of newly diagnosed cases could increase by over 40% by 2040—the project aims to identify barriers that prevent the uptake of sustainable behaviour changes in order to implement targeted interventions. Planned interventions include:

- ❖ Information and Guidance: A comprehensive pool of informational materials, along with personalized guidance and feedback delivered by health professionals.
- ❖ Digital Tool: The development of the MELIORA Intelligent Virtual Coach, which will offer context-sensitive and personalized advice via a mobile and web application.

The approach of the MELIORA Project involves several key steps: targeting (identifying women at risk), translation (adapting message characteristics and constraints), context-sensitive guidance (providing individualised advice based on cultural, financial, geographical, and other contexts), and monitoring and adaptation (both passive and active monitoring to assess goal compliance and adapt the feedback loop accordingly).

The methodology of the project was presented, dividing the actions into three phases:

- ❖ Knowledge acquisition (WP3): Literature reviews, situational analysis, co-creation & engagement, stakeholder workshops.
- ❖ Intervention development (WP4-5-6): Information material, personalized guidance and feedback, delivered by health professionals & the MELIORA Virtual Coach.
- ❖ Intervention and evaluation (WP7): Cluster randomized studies with 2000+ participants in 4 countries

All of these steps necessitate supportive local policies to facilitate access for diverse populations and groups, aiming to enhance motivation and address context in order to increase capabilities and opportunities. To ensure structured and comprehensive stakeholder engagement, the project will implement several advisory boards, including four local Stakeholder Policy Advisory Boards (SPABs) in Greece, Spain, Lithuania, and Sweden, along with one European SPAB.

The stakeholders will be divided into two main groups: implementers (including policymakers, health authorities, non-clinical health professionals, policy experts, and researchers) and end-users (such as breast cancer patients and patient representatives). It was noted that health authorities represented in the four local SPABs will be invited to join the European Board to foster a comprehensive and reciprocal stakeholder engagement strategy.

MELIORA provided an overview of the SPAB, which is tasked with advising on MELIORA intervention development to ensure the sustainability of project results. The aims of the board are as follow:

- ❖ Identifying gaps and needs in European breast cancer prevention programmes and policy.
- ❖ Maximising the replicability and scalability of the project's outcomes.
- ❖ Integrating the good practices from MELIORA into European and national cancer prevention plans.

This board is expected to participate in at least four virtual meetings throughout the project and may also be invited to participate in policy events. They will guide the development of the final policy conference and participate in the MELIORA policy debate during Breast Cancer Awareness Month in 2024.

7.2.2 Annual policy recommendations

Healthcare Coverage

- ❖ Funding allocation for healthcare systems: promote the allocation of sufficient public funds towards healthcare systems to mitigate staff shortages, particularly in oncology, reduce treatment waiting times, and lower out-of-pocket costs for patients.
- ❖ Universal healthcare coverage: ensure national level universal healthcare coverage covers the entire population, including vulnerable groups, such as Roma, migrants, and asylum seekers.
- ❖ Counteract redeployments of the EU health budget: To further deliver on the EU's Beating Cancer Plan, sufficient and dedicated funding needs to stay available. Additionally, enough health programmes need to be launched by the European Commission to ensure no available budget remains unspent.
- ❖ Budget allocation to prevention efforts: Increase budget allocations to breast cancer prevention efforts and ensure that Member States dedicate a specific portion of health spending on prevention efforts every year.

Access to Care

- ❖ Improving proximity to care: increase investment to enhance access to healthcare facilities, particularly for breast cancer screening and treatment in rural areas where a quarter of the EU population resides.

- ❖ Addressing the workforce crisis in cancer care: combat workforce shortages and uneven distribution in cancer care across the EU by investing in specialized training, upskilling programs, and supporting cross-border mobility and retention schemes.
- ❖ Enhancing access to digital health services: expand access to digital health services, prioritizing digital literacy and internet access, especially for population groups like the elderly, with low digital literacy skills.
- ❖ Improving access to health prevention tools for under-served populations: allocate resources to expand access to preventive healthcare tools in underserved populations, addressing key barriers to early prevention and treatment.

Health Literacy and Availability of Information

- ❖ Targeted awareness campaigns: design awareness campaigns tailored to different educational levels, highlighting screening importance, as screening participation rates vary significantly based on education.
- ❖ Risk-focused information for specific populations: direct awareness efforts toward specific risk groups, such as post-menopausal women who are overweight or obese.
- ❖ Multilingual and culturally sensitive information: ensure awareness and prevention materials are available in all relevant languages and adapted to cultural contexts across EU Member States.
- ❖ Accessible information on prevention and treatment: simplify and expand information related to cancer prevention and treatment, ensuring it is accessible, evidence-based, and free from jargon to engage a broad audience.
- ❖ Public education on health literacy: strengthen public education efforts around diet, weight control, screening, and treatment to enhance the public's understanding of cancer prevention and care.

Promoting Healthy Lifestyles

- ❖ Combatting sedentary lifestyles: as sedentary behaviour is a major breast cancer risk factor, prioritise initiatives that promote active lifestyles and activities such as active transportation (e.g., cycling, walking) under frameworks like the New European Urban Mobility Framework.

- ❖ Supporting healthy dietary habits: promote daily consumption of fruits and vegetables and educate on the benefits of a balanced diet as part of cancer prevention strategies.

Funding for healthy behaviour initiatives:

- ❖ National level: allocate resources to grassroots and community organisations to support accessible, subsidised physical activities, enabling equitable access to exercise and movement education.
- ❖ Local level: fund initiatives that create safe, green community spaces, encouraging outdoor activity and healthy living. For example, policies like “car-free Sundays” to foster active lifestyles.
- ❖ Promoting green spaces: invest in urban green spaces, which are linked to improved psychosocial and physical health behaviours in children, adolescents, and the elderly, providing social integration opportunities and access to healthier food options.

Healthy Environments

- ❖ Addressing air pollution: implement policies targeting air pollution, particularly in urban areas, to mitigate its link to increased breast cancer risk due to exposure to particulate matter.

Social Network Support

- ❖ Integrating social support in cancer care: facilitate the involvement of patients’ social networks by offering guidance on supportive practices, information to counter misinformation, and factual resources to alleviate fear.

Addressing Gaps in Screening Programs

- ❖ Expansion and standardisation of mammography services: increase investment in mammography units and equipment, as there is a seven-fold disparity in availability across EU countries.

- ❖ Standardisation of screening procedures: harmonise breast cancer screening protocols across EU Member States, covering aspects like screening frequency, target age groups, and procedural practices, guided by the [European Commission Initiative on Breast Cancer \(ECIBC\)](#).
- ❖ Risk-based screening programs: adapt screening programs to individual risk levels, modifying frequency, age range, and methods to enhance effectiveness, reduce costs, and minimize potential harms.

Research and Data Collection

- ❖ Data standardisation and collection: standardise breast cancer data collection across EU Member States to provide a comprehensive understanding of breast cancer prevalence, survival rates, and treatment outcomes. Currently, countries like Greece lack essential data, which is available in Sweden, Lithuania, and Spain.
- ❖ Integration of precision medicine: incorporate precision medicine, including whole genome sequencing, to identify targetable mutations for individualised cancer treatments.
- ❖ Development of immunoprevention tactics: provide funding for research on and implementation of immunoprevention approaches, such as vaccines for non-viral cancer prevention, as a promising avenue in cancer control.

Monitoring and Evaluation of Policies

- ❖ Support for policy standardisation across Member States: enhance EU support for the standardisation and monitoring of health policies at both EU and national levels to ensure uniformity in quality and access to cancer prevention and care.

7.3 iBeChange

7.3.1 Annual Cluster Summary

Denis Horgan (EAPM) chaired this session. The main outcome is the identification of persistent gaps and structuring the subsequent policy recommendations. A SWOT analysis must focus on the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats, particularly:

- ❖ Strength:

- Evidence-based Interventions: Current prevention strategies are grounded in evidence-based models, ensuring scientific backing and effectiveness.
 - Comprehensive Data Sharing: There is a strong emphasis on creating data-sharing platforms, facilitating collaboration between healthcare providers and stakeholders.
 - Focus on Emotions and Mental Health: Addressing psychological factors like anxiety and depression is crucial in cancer prevention and other chronic disease management.
 - AI Integration: AI-enhanced platforms allow for personalized prevention strategies, adjusting interventions based on user data, risk factors, and engagement.
- ❖ Weakness:
- Limited Accessibility: AI-driven solutions and personalised interventions may not be accessible to all populations, particularly in low-resource areas.
 - Fragmented Policies: The absence of standardised, cross-national policies often leads to inconsistent implementation of prevention strategies across healthcare systems.
 - Data Privacy Concerns: Sharing patient data raises concerns about data security and patient consent, potentially limiting collaboration.
 - High Costs: Many advanced technologies (e.g., AI, telehealth) are expensive to implement, making it difficult for smaller healthcare providers to adopt them.
- ❖ Opportunities:
- Expansion of Telehealth Services: The rise of digital health platforms provides an opportunity to expand prevention services to remote and underserved communities.
 - Policy Support for Mental Health Integration: Policy initiatives supporting the integration of mental health services into primary care can enhance prevention efforts by addressing both physical and emotional health.
 - Global Health Collaborations: International organisations like WHO and OECD can facilitate broader adoption of successful prevention programmes across regions through policy enablers and funding.

- Public Health Campaigns: Awareness campaigns focusing on behavioural and lifestyle changes can help populations adopt healthier habits, reducing long-term healthcare costs.

❖ Threats:

- Regulatory Barriers: Complex regulatory environments may slow down the adoption of AI-based and data-driven prevention tools, especially in data-sensitive regions.
- Resistance to Change: Healthcare providers and patients may be resistant to adopting new technologies or shifting away from traditional models of care.
- Health Disparities: Social, economic, and regional disparities can limit the effectiveness of prevention strategies, particularly in underfunded healthcare systems.
- Cybersecurity Risks: With the increasing reliance on digital data-sharing platforms, there is a growing risk of data breaches and cyberattacks, which could undermine trust in prevention initiatives.

DH also presented a comprehensive list of the key gaps identified so far and the subsequent mitigation strategies to be implemented to overcome them.

7.3.2 Annual Policy Recommendations

Accessibility to Advanced Technology

- ❖ Gap: AI and telehealth technologies may not reach low-resource regions.
- ❖ Mitigation: Introduce lower-cost or subsidised models of AI and telehealth platforms for resource-limited settings, potentially funded by international aid or public-private partnerships.

Inconsistent Policy Implementation

- ❖ Gap: Fragmented policies across different regions hinder a unified approach to prevention.
- ❖ Mitigation: Foster international collaborations to establish standardised prevention policies, with a focus on adaptable frameworks suitable for diverse healthcare systems.

Data Privacy and Security Concerns

- ❖ Gap: Worries about patient data security slow down collaborative efforts.
- ❖ Mitigation: Implement stringent security protocols and transparent consent mechanisms to protect patient data while promoting collaboration between healthcare entities.

Cost Barriers

- ❖ Gap: High costs associated with AI, personalised medicine, and advanced prevention technologies.
- ❖ Mitigation: Encourage healthcare policies that incentivise the adoption of cost-effective preventive measures and provide subsidies for the implementation of new technologies in smaller practices.

To ensure uptake in the healthcare system, the following actions are foreseen under four main objectives:

- ❖ Community Engagement: Engage communities through education and outreach to increase the public's understanding and trust in preventive healthcare strategies (particularly AI-driven models).
- ❖ Training and Education: Provide healthcare professionals with comprehensive training on integrating AI and telehealth platforms into their daily practice.
- ❖ Incentives for Prevention: Develop reimbursement models that incentivise preventive care over reactive care.
- ❖ Public-Private Partnership: Governments can partner with private tech companies to offer affordable solutions for AI-driven prevention platforms in the public healthcare system.

To facilitate the success of the described action plan and the uptake of prevention, some policy enablers have been identified and described as follows:

- ❖ **Cross-National Data Sharing Agreement:** Promote international collaboration and data-sharing agreements that allow iBeChange to expand globally while maintaining high standards (privacy, security).
- ❖ **National Digital Health Strategies:** Advocate for national policies that support the adoption of AI and digital platforms in healthcare (particularly preventive care).
- ❖ **Incentivised Preventive Care Models:** Encourage governments to create policies facilitating healthcare interventions that include BC models.
- ❖ **Telehealth Integrations:** Leverage policies that promote telehealth as a vehicle for preventive care, integrating iBeChange with broader digital health initiatives at a national level.

8. Common Policy Themes

Enhancing Accessibility and Equity in Healthcare:

- ❖ Expand access to preventive healthcare, particularly for underserved populations, including rural and socioeconomically disadvantaged groups.
- ❖ Promote universal healthcare coverage to ensure inclusivity for vulnerable groups, such as migrants and minorities.
- ❖ Improve digital literacy and access to digital health tools to reduce inequities.

Promoting Health Literacy and Public Awareness:

- ❖ Develop community-focused educational programs to enhance public understanding of preventive health measures.
- ❖ Tailor health campaigns to diverse demographics, ensuring multilingual, culturally sensitive, and evidence-based materials.
- ❖ Conduct awareness campaigns to address modifiable risk factors such as diet, sedentary lifestyles, smoking and alcohol consumption.

Strengthening Workforce and Training Initiatives:

- ❖ Invest in specialized training and upskilling programs for healthcare professionals, including the integration of AI and telehealth technologies.

- ❖ Address healthcare workforce shortages through retention schemes and cross-border mobility programs.

Prioritizing Preventive Care and Healthy Lifestyles:

- ❖ Create reimbursement models that incentivize preventive care over reactive treatments.
- ❖ Fund initiatives to encourage active lifestyles, healthy dietary habits, and utilization of urban green spaces.
- ❖ Promote risk-based and personalized screening programs for conditions like breast cancer.

Advancing Digital and Telehealth Solutions:

- ❖ Integrate telehealth into national healthcare strategies, emphasizing preventive care.
- ❖ Support AI-driven healthcare tools and digital platforms to improve accessibility and efficiency.
- ❖ Address data privacy and cybersecurity concerns to build public trust in digital health solutions.

Fostering Multistakeholder Collaboration:

- ❖ Facilitate partnerships between governments, private entities, and community organizations to drive innovation and policy reform.
- ❖ Encourage cross-national data-sharing agreements to enhance research and health outcomes while ensuring strict privacy standards.

Standardizing Policies and Practices:

- ❖ Harmonize healthcare policies and preventive practices across regions to reduce disparities and improve implementation.
- ❖ Standardize data collection and healthcare protocols for better monitoring and evaluation.

Integrating Mental Health into Preventive Strategies:

- ❖ Include mental health support within preventive care frameworks, addressing the psychological aspects of health and well-being.
- ❖ Co-create mental health services with user input to ensure relevance and accessibility.

Expanding Research and Innovation:

- ❖ Fund research into precision medicine, immunoprevention, and digital health technologies.
- ❖ Support collaborative frameworks that involve citizens and patients in shaping preventive healthcare solutions.

Strengthening Public Health Campaigns:

- ❖ Launch national and local campaigns to raise awareness about lifestyle-related risk factors and preventive measures.
- ❖ Use community engagement models to promote sustainable behavioural changes.

These recommendations emphasize a holistic approach to preventive healthcare, integrating accessibility, innovation, public awareness, and stakeholder collaboration to create equitable and effective health systems.

9. Common Policy Themes

These policy recommendations are aimed at transforming healthcare systems into more equitable, efficient, and prevention-focused frameworks. By prioritizing **accessibility and equity**, underserved populations such as rural communities and vulnerable groups will benefit from improved healthcare access and outcomes. Universal healthcare coverage and enhanced digital literacy efforts would not only address systemic inequities but also empower individuals to actively participate in their health management, potentially reducing long-term costs and alleviating the strain on reactive care systems.

Promoting health literacy and public awareness is expected to yield substantial benefits by encouraging earlier detection of diseases and healthier lifestyles. Tailored and culturally sensitive educational initiatives can engage diverse communities more effectively, ensuring widespread participation in preventive programs. Awareness campaigns that target modifiable risk factors, like unhealthy diet, sedentary behaviour, alcohol consumption, and smoking could significantly lower the incidence of cancer.

The focus on **workforce development and training initiatives** would address critical shortages and skill gaps in healthcare, especially in high-need areas like oncology and preventive medicine. Upskilling professionals in AI and telehealth technologies would enable the integration of cutting-edge solutions, improving care delivery efficiency and outcomes. Additionally, retention and mobility schemes could ensure a balanced distribution of skilled professionals across regions, minimizing disparities in care quality.

Advancing **digital health and telehealth solutions** could revolutionize how healthcare is delivered, especially for remote or underserved populations. Integrating AI and telehealth into national strategies would not only enhance preventive care but also streamline processes and reduce costs. Addressing cybersecurity and privacy concerns is crucial to foster public trust in these technologies, which could see broader adoption and greater impact as trust is established.

Finally, fostering **multistakeholder collaboration** and **standardizing policies and practices** could ensure consistent and scalable healthcare solutions across regions. Collaborative frameworks would align goals among governments, private entities, and community organizations, amplifying the reach and effectiveness of interventions. Standardized data collection and health protocols could improve monitoring, research outcomes, and policy evaluations, creating a feedback loop for continuous improvement.

In essence, these recommendations promise a holistic, transformative impact by addressing immediate healthcare inequities, investing in future-focused technologies, and fostering a cultural shift towards prevention and well-being. The integration of diverse strategies ensures a robust approach, capable of addressing the multifaceted challenges of modern healthcare systems.

10. Conclusions

The collaborative Prevention Cluster, through the iBeChange, MELIORA, and SUNRISE projects, is advancing the EU Cancer Mission's goals by focusing on sustainable behavioural

change, digital engagement, and addressing healthcare inequalities. Coordinated interventions and shared learnings are anticipated to improve cancer prevention efforts and support policies that benefit public health and fight cancer across Europe.

The conclusion of the first annual cluster meeting included an update on the activities carried out for the citizen engagement and the addressing inequalities strand.

10.1 Citizen engagement & addressing inequalities: Annual update

The objective of the strand on citizen engagement is to ensure that the research and interventions that result from the three projects accurately reflect the real needs and lived experiences of those most affected by cancer. By actively engaging patients and the wider public, we can bridge the gap between scientific research and societal impact, ensuring that the solutions we develop are not only scientifically sound but also practical, accessible, and meaningful for diverse communities. The strand has been launched during the annual cluster meeting 2024. Therefore, only separate actions by the different projects have been undertaken so far. However, in the near future, this strand will be supported through the implementation of workshops, working groups, and expert panels where citizens can share their experiences and opinions; through the establishment of advisory boards to ensure a structured mechanism for patient voices to be heard; patient feedback through the dissemination of surveys; and gathering patient testimonies via video, email, and interviews to incorporate the voices of cancer patients and survivors. For instance, MELIORA will involve patient representatives in the next MELIORA Policy-debate that will take place on November the 20th at 5pm CET (with representatives from Europa Donna Greece). At the cluster level, together, SUNRISE, MELIORA and iBeChange will consider the added value of focus groups or workshops where citizens can share their experiences and opinions on lifestyle changes, mental health, and emotional management. For the next annual cluster meeting, the projects will consider involving patients and patient advocates, who are related to each one of the projects. In addition, once the projects present some progress in their development, several rounds of presentations for patients will be organised. These presentations will be adapted to their individual profiles and will open conversation and feedback loops via surveys.

The objective of the strand on Addressing Inequalities is to ensure effective collaboration among the three projects focused on addressing inequalities in access to care, sustainable behavioural change, and enhancing cancer prevention. This will be supported by creating synergies between cluster projects, building on recommendations and findings from previous projects, reviewing existing literature, and utilising developed tools. To facilitate these efforts,

bi-monthly meetings are scheduled to discuss the progress, gather feedback, and address common challenges. A preliminary identification of commonalities has been developed through a screening of the variables collected across the various projects, which will be further analysed to integrate the data and produce the expected outcomes. The identified common aspects will facilitate the development of key expected outcomes, together with the information gathered through the cluster's collaborative efforts - encompassing meeting minutes, best practices, evaluation and progress reports, co-created tools, and outcome materials.

10.2 Annual cluster meeting conclusions and next steps

The first annual meeting of the Prevention Cluster has underscored the critical role of collaboration in advancing cancer prevention and behavioural change strategies across Europe. The projects within the cluster—iBeChange, MELIORA, and SUNRISE—have demonstrated impressive progress, particularly in digital health innovation, addressing health inequalities, and implementing comprehensive communication strategies. Notably, the establishment of regular cluster meetings is set to strengthen ongoing collaboration and streamline efforts across the various strands. By identifying best practices, analysing shared variables, and conducting a scoping review, partners aim to build an evidence-based foundation that supports robust policy recommendations and effective interventions.

Following the meeting, key action points were successfully completed: Nathan Lea (i-HD - iBeChange) assumed leadership of the Data Management strand, working closely with IEO (iBeChange Project) Coordinator) and partners from MELIORA and SUNRISE to enhance data integration and streamline management protocols. Additionally, the Scientific Work Plan for the cluster was collaboratively drafted and delivered on time, reflecting a unified scientific direction across consortia. These updates, alongside efforts to establish regular cluster meetings, define best practices, analyse shared data, and develop a literature repository, underscore the cluster's commitment to a cohesive, evidence-based approach.

The next steps will focus on addressing these challenges through greater synergies, targeted policy alignment, and cross-project collaboration, including joint publications, mapping of partner expertise, and the establishment of data protection protocols compliant with GDPR and other regulations. These activities are pivotal for fostering a unified approach, which is essential for translating research findings into actionable strategies. The success of the Prevention Cluster ultimately hinges on continuous communication, shared learning, and a

cohesive strategy that aligns with Europe's Beating Cancer Plan to maximise its impact on cancer prevention and health outcomes across Europe.

Overall, the recommendations that have been outlined in this document provide a robust framework for addressing gaps in cancer prevention at the individual, national, and EU level with the purpose of informing and supporting effective decision-making. Grounded in current policy frameworks on the EU and Member State level, the projects within the Prevention and Early Detection Cluster present results that have been shaped by iterative research processes, including workshops, surveys, advisory board consultations, and annual cluster meetings. In this regard, the collective recommendations not only incorporate the needs of stakeholder groups- including healthcare providers, cancer patients, survivors, advocacy organisations, and policymakers themselves- but they also reflect these diverse perspectives. Each project focuses on a critical aspect, ranging from community education to screening accessibility, resulting in a comprehensive, evidence-informed, collaborative and unified front for European, national, and local legislative bodies to carry forward to reduce the burden of cancer and improve quality of life.

Although these recommendations provide a solid starting point, further consultation and collaboration is needed between the projects and among external stakeholders and experts. In this way, the recommendations can continue to be refined in ways that accurately reflect current gaps and legislative updates. A revised version of this document and the recommendations within will be presented after the 2nd annual meeting of the Prevention and Early Detection (behavioural change) cluster, and a final version will be presented after the 4th annual meeting of the cluster. In the meantime, each version of the recommendations will be publicly available to allow for further stakeholder feedback and consultations.

Appendix

Table 11: Prevention and early detection cluster annual meeting Agenda

SEPTEMBER 17 th - Cluster Meeting – 09:30 - 13:00		
Topic	Speaker	Time
Greetings and Welcome	Gabriella Pravettoni (IEO)	09.30 - 09:40
Opening session	Laura Garcia Ibanez (HADEA)	09:40 - 10:00
<i>Q&A</i>	<i>All representatives</i>	<i>10 minutes</i>
Research Updates from the Cluster's Project		
iBeChange	Gabriella Pravettoni and Marianna Masiero	10:10 - 10:20
Meliora	Yannios Manios and Niki Mourouti	10:20 -10:30
Sunrise	Konstantinos Votis and Andreas Triantafyllidis	10:30 - 10:40
<i>Q&A</i>	<i>All representatives</i>	<i>10 minutes</i>
Coffee Break 10: 50 – 11:05		
Progress Updates on Cluster Activities		
■ Addressing Inequalities	MELIORA - Justine van de Feen and Frans Folkvord, PBY	11:05 - 11:20
■ Communication and Dissemination	EAPM /eCancer (IBeCHANGE)	11:20 - 11:35
■ R&I strand including the Common Scientific Workplan and the Policy recommendations	Lucas Javier Segal (PBY) and Delia Nicoara – IOCN (Sunrise)	11:35-11: 50
■ Open issues: Data Management and Citizen engagement.	<i>All representatives</i>	11: 50 - 12:00
Annual policy recommendations of the Prevention: ROUND TABLE Chair: Denis Horgan (EAPM)		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ SWOT Analysis of how they are tackling Prevention ■ What are the gaps and how to mitigate these? ■ How to ensure uptake in healthcare systems? ■ What are the policy enablers to facilitate this? 	iBeChange - Denis Horgan	12:00-12:10
	Meliora - Dolores Cvitanin	12:10-12:20
	Sunrise - Delia Nicoara	12:20-12:30
	<i>Q&A</i>	<i>All representatives</i>

Discussion: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Common elements that the EU should take Specific elements for LMIC, and minority groups 	<i>EAPM</i> – Denis Horgan	12:40 - 12:55
Any Other Business (AOB) and Conclusions	Gabriella Pravettoni	12:55 - 13:00

Table 12: Online Attendance List

Name	Team/project
Ambrosini Emilia	iBeChange, POLIMI
Bennardo William	iBeChange, POLIMI
Dui Linda Greta	iBeChange, POLIMI
Ferrante Simona	iBeChange, POLIMI
Piantella Davide	iBeChange, POLIMI
Laureanti Rita	iBeChange, POLIMI
Ghiold Diana	iBeChange, SIMAVI
Oana Carmen	iBeChange, SIMAVI
Popescu Radu	iBeChange, SIMAVI
Martín Núria Vives	iBeChange, ICO
Amram Denise	iBeChange, IEAB
Cavolo Alice	iBeChange, IEAB
Songhorian Sarah	iBeChange, IEAB
Lopez Ana Beatriz	iBeChange, SD
Machiavelli Aline	iBeChange, SD
Martina Fontana	iBeChange, EAB
Britt Sandberg	BCF AMAZONA
Monika	SWPS Poland

Nikos Sarris	MELIORA, CERTH
Alexandra Olson	MELIORA, EHMA
Dominika Wietryzkowska	MELIORA, SWPS
Gintarė Kalinienė	MELIORA, LSMU
Eva Karaglanı	MELIORA, HUA
Giuseppe Martone	MELIORA, EHMA
Linda Engström	MELIORA, BCF Amazona
Laurène Mathey	MELIORA, EHMA
Linda Greta Dui	
Mireia Gandia Prat	MELIORA, FISABIO
Rita Laureanti	
Teresa de Pablo Pardo	SUNRISE, FISABIO
Dolores Cviticanin	MELIORA, EHMA
Christina Pelekanou	MELIORA, HUA
Anna Gavrieli	MELIORA, HUA
Niki Mourouti	MELIORA, HUA
Nina Nicoara	IOCN
Yannis Manios	MELIORA, HUA
Marina Pinto Carbó	MELIORA, FISABIO
Ana Molina Barceló	MELIORA, FISABIO
Davide Piantella	
Nina McGrath	MELIORA, EUFIC
Theophano Pampaka	PASYKAF- SUNRISE
Kay Duggan-Walls	
Jan-Willem van de Loo	

Ana Miralles Marco	MELIORA, INCLIVA
Paula Romeo Cervera	